

The Fourth to Eighth Levels of Meditation Absorption can be Attained Through the Practice of Anapanasati and Space Kasina Meditation Techniques in the Context of Buddhist Meditation for Chakras System

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Abstract: The study of the spiritual life and souls protocol using the Buddhist meditation approach for growth of chakras and cosmic power control, healing, and therapeutic treatment of healthy symptoms the chakras 1–7 were found in the body cavity and directly related to the nervous system with meditation absorption level 4 by using the Anapanasati practice, but not the highest for meditation method. Buddhist meditation is divided into nine levels, but only eight levels have the ability to grow with the common people by using Kasina practice. Kasina practice consisted of meditation devices and was divided into 10 subjects. However, in terms of growth and understanding, the Kasina meditation was extremely difficult to obtain. So, this paper aims to propose the Space Kasina for growth at meditation absorption level 8 (Treasure 8) and to describe the condition feature.

Keywords: Chakras, meditation, Spiritual life, Anapanasati, Space Kasina, cosmic power.

I. INTRODUCTION

Anapanasati practice, according to the study of Buddhist meditation for spiritual life and souls for healing, caring, and healthy benefit. The Anapanasati practice was the highest level of meditation absorption, with one mind at level 4 (Malimas et al., 2023). The chakra system is controlled by using the meditation absorption at level 4, but it is not so easy to control. The higher meditation absorption, more than meditation absorption at level 4, was described in Tipitaka with Kasina practice and called Jhana 8 or Treasure 8.

The Kasina meditation devices are separated into 10 subjects, including the 4 Elements Kasina, such as the Earth Kasina, the Water Kasina, the Fire Kasina, and the Wind Kasina. Blue Kasina, Yellow Kasina, Red Kasina, and White kasina are the four different colors of Kasina. The other Kasinas, including the Light Kasina and the Space Kasina, The Kasina was used to remember mind and mindfulness by pointing or focusing at the photograph when both eyes were closed.

The photography vision was presented and changed to a new special form. The mild ability to control it was at meditation absorption level 4, and after that, the meditation will be growing to meditation absorption level 8. However, the Kasina finds it extremely difficult to complete until it gives a clear description of the meditation condition.

So, this study aims to propose the description of meditation absorption level 4-8, in Buddhist meditation by using Anapanasati and Space Kasina practices, respectively.

II. BODY OF ARTICLE

Method

Anapanasati Practice

The Anapanasati practice in the context of the Tipitaka and the paracanonical Pali texts the practice involves focusing on the breath at three different locations, namely the nose tip, chest, and abdomen, in order to develop mindfulness and concentration (Thomus and Cohen, 2014; Millière et al., 2018; Nash et al., 2013; Deolindo et al., 2020; Nash and Newberg, 2023). The mindfulness was following the breathing in and out from the nose tip to the chest and abdomen, respectively. The breathing in and out were natural activity conditions, not controlled and focused outside the body by the mindfulness. The final meditation of this practice was meditation absorption level 4. When finished, the slow return to the first step of meditation was necessary; mindfulness was known from top to bottom and returned with the five times for repetition, this step setting the ground stage before meditation condition.

Space Kasina Practice

The mind and mindfulness were focusing at the abdomen, as Chakra 3 in the Chakras system, and the pointing of the space spot at the cavity of the body was growth from the dark spot until the space circle was presented, and following the circle change to the white light circle, the glass circle form continued to the feeling of not having presented the body or the dissolved body, respectively. This meditation reduced the time to 1–3 hours for the meditation. When finished, a slow return to the first step of meditation was necessary, as was the Anapanasati practice.

Results

Anapanasati practice

The meditation was the initial step to treat or clear the condition, with the mindfulness not looking at breathing but feeling to know all the body condition first. This step took maybe 3-5 minutes, and after that, the mindfulness focused on breathing in and out at the nose tip, chest, and abdomen, respectively.

The second step, the mindfulness, was found in the breathing in and out at the nose tip to the chest and abdomen only and standing firm to know; this step used about 10-15 minutes of the part of meditation.

The third step was the deep meditation absorption. In this step, the mindfulness was focused on only one position of the breathing attached and included four levels. In this study, we focused on the abdomen, or Chakra 3 in the chakra system, because this Chakra is very strong and easy to control the energy and the mind as we bring mindfulness to the final stages of meditation.

The absorption level 1, or Jhana 1 condition presented to the body was a little movement to adjust and lock the muscle and skeleton of the body. The mindfulness found the abdomen collapsed and puffing up. When breathing was the result, the abdomen collapsed, and puffing up was the income.

The absorption level 2, or Jhana 2 was presented with a variety of conditions, such as orange color light and loss, the sensation of body movement, expand and shrink. Sometime the white light and circle were found, and many conditions and losses occurred within a short time. The energy was presented, covering the body, and appearing to flare up quickly. The practice of mindfulness was recognized as a conditional activity, but it was not controlled.

Deep meditation was the next step after the many conditions presented in absorption level 2. This condition was very happy, or a good, comfortable feeling. When most people reach this point, their minds simply stop for a long time. However when the mindfulness known about this was only common meditation level 3 or Jhana3, the meditation was following meditation absorption level 4.

The final step of meditation absorption at level 4, or Jhana4 of Anapanasati practice was focusing mindfulness on the indifferent only, and the body was comfortable with this step where the mind and the body were clearly separated.

The Anapanasati practice was finished only with meditation absorption limited to level 4, as one mind. The highest energy of the mind was successfully absorbed, and this meditation helped to develop special senses when making the meditation. Hold this step every time you get to meditation. However, the initial meditation absorption step to level 4 may have found the force inside the body and felt deep meditation, the rapid heart rate looked like extinction, and this step may not have been easy to pass.

Space Kasina practice

The meditation with the mind and mindfulness was focusing on the abdomen as Chakra 3, which is in the abdomen below the navel inside the body cavity.

The first step, 1–5 minutes of small focusing, was presented. This step is called the meditation step.

The second step, 10-15 minutes, is when the mind and mindfulness are at their strongest. The focusing or pointing of the space in the cavity of the body was firm and presented in the dark spot photograph of the vision focusing on Chakra 3.

The third, the body, had a little movement while it adjusted and locked the muscle and skeleton of the body, and the photograph vision looked like a gray-colored smoke circle. This step was meditation absorption level 1, or Jhana 1.

The meditation absorption level 2, or Jhana 2 was presented with deep feeling and standing firm to the gray color of the white smoke circle, after which the orange color light was presented and the feeling to the body's movements, expansion, and contraction. Sometime, the white light and circle energy were found, and many conditions and losses appeared within a short period of time. The mind and mindfulness continued despite these conditions, but they did not undo the meditation. The white smoke circle was presented again, focusing the mind, and encouraging mindfulness.

The meditation absorption level 3, or Jhana3, was presented. Deep meditation followed the orange light circle, and then a change to a white light circle was presented. The happiness emotion is presented with a good, comfortable feeling; this feeling looks like deep sleep in an air-conditioned room, but it is not sleep; the mind and mindfulness are activated every time.

The meditation absorption level 4, or Jhana 4, was presented, the glass circle was presented and covering the body, and the focusing of the small white spot was presented at the middle of the body. The emotion was indifferent only, and the body was comfortable at this step. The mind and the body were separated.

The meditation absorption level 5, or Jhana5, presented the losses of the circle photograph vision; the space was presented in the abdomen and expanded to cover the body and extend outside the body; the emotion felt to be the emptying of the body; everything until the world. But the mind and mindfulness knew this was only a temporary empty condition in the meditation.

The meditation was following meditation absorption level 6, or Jhana 6, with the empty condition, and the spaces were returning to the abdomen and standing firm. Following that, the photograph vision was presented to two people who were standing opposite each other and looking at a person's photograph vision until it dissolved. However, this step may not have presented the person with photographic vision, but it did present the mind linked or contacting everything inside and outside

the body in a short period of time. Mindfulness is the movement of the mind and the body. So, this step was presented as mind, mindfulness, and the body closely related to 3 parts.

The meditation absorption level 7 was presented to the mind in a very short time. The mindfulness was free-falling but known to the mind and body in the short time. This condition changed in a short time, and the mind and body were clearly separated to 3 parts.

The final level of meditation was meditation absorption level 8 or Treasure 8, which appears to be like meditation absorption level 7 at times, but the feeling with the mindfulness does not interest the mind and the body, and the mind does not interest the mindfulness and the body. After feeling to the body was dissolved and presented only free activity of the mind and mindfulness, two parts presented only.

When the mediation absorption level 8 was completed, the fullness of the mediation was presented, and the mediation was terminated. The gradual withdrawal of meditation was important because it allowed the nervous system and peripheral nerve system to return to their original state. So, the numbness symptom may be present, with 1-3 hours for the mediation time.

The meditation absorption level 8 is very important for controlling and seeing the wheel of chakra rotation with the photograph vision and is used for studying the plan and rotation of the chakra system in the Taoism protocol for the cosmic power studies feature.

III. CONCLUSION

The Anapanasati practice ability to focus on mindfulness is limited to meditation absorption level 4, with emotion and condition based on the meditation absorption concerning the Tipitaka book, with the alignment of the meditation absorption level from the initial stage, secondary stage, and the third with deep meditation stage, respectively. The Anapanasati practice ability, on the other hand, focuses on three positions of the attached breathing apparatus, namely the nose tip, chest, and abdomen. The nose tip was focusing mindfulness and mind pointed at Chakra 6. This position was the third-eye chakra, which is in the forebrain, in the thalamus area, hypothalamus, pineal gland, and pituitary gland, which affects the opening of the third eye in the chakra system. When the breathing was attached at the chest by mindfulness focusing, the high energy was presented and pointed to Chakra 4. This chakra was the channel of emotion responding transferred from the conversation person and effected to Chakra 6 for thinking and emotion reaction to follow.

The Space Kasina was the focal point of the space spot in the cavity body at the abdomen, or Chakra 3 of the chakra system. The photograph vision was the protocol for the focusing of the mind and mindfulness from the first to the final step as the meditation absorption level 8. The conditions of the meditation step change every short time. At meditation absorption levels 1-4, the photograph vision of smoke circle formation appeared, but not at levels 5-8.

This result was considered and referred to in the Tipitaka book, as the meditation absorption levels 1-4 were presented through the photographic vision, but the meditation absorption levels 5-8 were not presented through the focusing of the mind and mindfulness.

The meditation absorption levels 4–8 used for comic power studies with the wheel chakras do not respond well to the lower levels of meditation absorption, because the low energy of mind power does not completely control them. Although meditation absorption can control the Chakras, it has not been as successful in observing the wheel Chakras photograph vision.

So, the meditation absorption necessary for cosmic power studies occurs with wheel chakra system observation.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest.

Author contributions

Both authors contributed equally to this work and approved it for publication. T. M (1). and A. S., designed the study. All the authors perform the experiments. T. M (1)., K. Y., and M. J, prepared the manuscript in the study. T. M (2), P. R., and T. P., instructed the experiment. The detailed discussion were made among nine.

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